

THE EFFECT OF GROWTH REGULATORS ON THE PROPAGATION OF POMEGRANATE CULTIVARS FROM GREEN CUTTINGS

Ochildiyev Jahongir Mengdobilovich

Deputy Director for Research and Innovation, Surkhandarya Research and Experimental Station, Academician M. Mirzaev Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking

Email: bogdod92@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0007-0273-1658

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Abstract: This article details the technology for propagating the pomegranate cultivars 'Kirmizi kabuh', 'Zubayda-667', and 'Gyulashe' from green cuttings in artificial misting facilities under the climatic conditions of the Denov district, Surkhandarya region. The study investigated the effect of various concentrations (1–8 ml/l) of the growth regulator "Zircon" on the rooting and subsequent biometric indicators of the cuttings. The results showed that a concentration of 5 ml/l was the optimal rate for all cultivars, with the 'Gyulashe' cultivar demonstrating the highest rooting percentage (93.2%).

Keywords: pomegranate, green cutting, artificial mist, "Zircon," rooting, biometric indicators, substrate.

Abstract: This article describes the propagation technology for the pomegranate varieties 'Kirmizi kabuh', 'Zubayda-667', and 'Gyulashe' using cuttings within artificial misting facilities under the climatic conditions of the Denov district, Surkhandarya region. The study investigated the effect of various concentrations (1–8 ml/l) of the growth regulator 'Zircon' on the rooting and subsequent biometric parameters of the cuttings. The results indicated that a 5 ml/l concentration was optimal for all varieties, with the 'Gyulashe' variety demonstrating the highest rooting rate (93.2%).

Keywords: pomegranate, cuttings, artificial mist, 'Zircon', rooting, biometric parameters, substrate.

Abstract: The article describes the technology for propagating the pomegranate varieties 'Kirmizi kabuh', 'Zubayda-667', and 'Gyulashe' in artificial mist-generating structures using green cuttings, under the climatic conditions of the Denov district, Surkhandarya region. During the study, the effect of different concentrations of the 'Zircon' growth regulator (1–8 ml/l) on the rooting and subsequent biometric indicators of the cuttings was examined. The results showed that a concentration of 5 ml/l was the most optimal for all varieties, and the 'Gyulashe' variety exhibited the highest rooting rate (93.2%).

Keywords: pomegranate, green cuttings, artificial mist, 'Zircon', rooting, biometric indicators, substrate.

INTRODUCTION. In Uzbekistan, the rapid development of pomegranate seedlings and bringing them to a standard condition within a single season is one of the most pressing tasks. Particularly in the Denov district of the Surxondaryo region, summer air temperatures rising to 35–40°C, along with a sharp decrease in relative humidity, lead to the dehydration and death of cuttings when using traditional propagation methods.

The use of artificial misting technologies is highly effective in solving this problem. Creating a mist reduces transpiration and establishes a favorable microclimate for root formation. This study scientifically substantiates the importance of growth stimulants in

cultivating high-quality seedlings from the green cuttings of promising pomegranate varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The research was conducted from 2020 to 2022 in a specialized nursery facility in the Denov district. The Kirmizi Kabuh, Zubayda-667, and Gyulashe pomegranate varieties were selected as the subjects of the experiment.

Experimental Setup:

- Number of replications: 4.
- Number of cuttings: 25 per variant, for a total of 2,700 cuttings.
- Substrate: A lower layer of biohumus and an upper layer of sand (1:1).
- Preparation: "Zircon" (in concentrations from 0 to 8 ml/l).
- Microclimate: Air humidity of 85-95%, temperature of 24-28°C. Nozzles were activated for 15 seconds every 15 minutes.

In mid-May, cuttings were prepared to a length of 15–18 cm, soaked in a "Zircon" solution for 12 hours, and then planted in the substrate.

Research results and discussion. Our experiments to determine the effect of treatment with various concentrations of the "Zircon" preparation on the rooting of pomegranate green cuttings showed that in all studied varieties, the rooting of green cuttings recorded higher rates compared to the control group treated with water.

Consequently, in the Kirmizi kabuh variety, the rooting rate for the control variant, i.e., where no preparation was applied, was 52.3%. This figure represents the natural rooting ability of this variety. When a solution with a concentration of 1 ml/l was applied, the rooting rate increased to 57.3%, showing a significant increase compared to the control. At 2 ml/l, this figure reached 62.4%, a result nearly 10 percentage points higher than the control. At a concentration of 3 ml/l, the rooting rate increased sharply to 74.8%. At 4 ml/l, the rate was 82.6%, and at 5 ml/l, the highest result was recorded at 88.9%. This represents an increase of 36.6 percentage points compared to the control. However, when the concentration was increased to 6-8 ml/l, the rooting rate decreased slightly, amounting to 84.5%, 84.3%, and 84.0%, respectively. This indicates that the optimal concentration is around 5 ml/l and that a higher dose does not increase effectiveness.

The Zubayda-667 variety showed similar, yet more effective results. In the control group, the rooting rate was 53.9%. At 1 ml/l, it reached 62.3%, and at 2 ml/l, it was 66.1%. At a concentration of 3 ml/l, 79.0% was recorded, and 86.4% at 4 ml/l. The highest result was observed at 5 ml/l, amounting to 91.7%. This indicates a figure 37.8 percentage points higher than the control. At 6 ml/l, 88.6% was recorded, 85.5% at 7 ml/l, and 85.2% at 8 ml/l. As can be seen, increasing the concentration up to 5 ml/l had a positive effect, after which a slight decrease occurred, but the rate still remained significantly higher than in the control group.

The table data show that the Gyulashe variety exhibited the highest results among all varieties. In the control group, its rooting rate was 55.1%, indicating a slightly higher natural rooting ability compared to other varieties. At 1 ml/l, it reached 63.7%, and at 2 ml/l, it was 68.8%. While the rooting rate was 81.5% at 3 ml/l, it increased to 88.9% at 4 ml/l. The highest figure was observed at a 5 ml/l concentration, amounting to 93.2%. This is the highest result in the table and represents an increase of 38.1 percentage points compared to the control. At 6-8 ml/l, the figure decreased slightly, amounting to 90.1%, 89.9%, and 89.3%, respectively, but nevertheless remained at a very high level (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Rooting of green cuttings of pomegranate varieties depending on "Sirkon" concentration, % (average, 2020–2022)

Varieties	Treatment variant								
	Water - control	1 ml/L	2 ml/L	3 ml/L	4 ml/L	5 ml/L	6 ml/L	7 ml/L	8 ml/L
Kirmizi Kabuh	52.3	57.3	62.4	74.8	82.6	88.9	84.5	84.3	84.0
Zubayda-667	53.9	62.3	66.1	79.0	86.4	91.7	88.6	85.5	85.2
Gyulashe	55.1	63.7	68.8	81.5	88.9	93.2	90.1	89.9	89.3

The general analysis shows that the application of the solution significantly increased the rooting percentage in all varieties. While the indicators in the control variant ranged from 52.3% to 55.1%, they reached 88.9–93.2% at the optimal concentration of 5 ml/L. Thus, the use of the preparation nearly doubled the rooting rate. For all varieties, 5 ml/L proved to be the most optimal rate, as higher concentrations did not increase effectiveness and, in some cases, slightly reduced it. A comparison between the varieties shows that the Gyulashe variety took the leading position in terms of rooting ability, Zubayda-667 ranked second, and Kirmizi Kabuh had relatively lower indicators.

Figure 1. Rooting of green cuttings of pomegranate varieties depending on "Sirkon" concentration, % (average, 2020–2022)

However, the trend was the same for all varieties: as the concentration increased, the positive effect intensified up to a certain threshold, and then stabilized or decreased. This indicates that during the root formation process, physiological and biochemical factors are activated within a specific optimal range (see Figure 1).

Conclusion. In the hot climate of the Surxondaryo region, the application of artificial misting technology and growth stimulants is essential for propagating pomegranates from green cuttings. A 5 ml/l concentration of the preparation "Zirkon" was identified as the most effective dose for all studied varieties.

Among the varieties, the "Gyulashe" variety was found to have the highest potential for rooting (93.2%) and biometric development. This technology makes it possible to grow high-quality, standard-grade pomegranate seedlings within a single season..

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